

QSAR study of novel inhibitors of human histone deacetylase with *in vivo* antitumor activity[†]

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Abstract : The paper describe modeling of log IC₅₀ representing *in vivo* antitumor activity using chemical as well as topological descriptors. The results have shown that the chemical descriptors are no useful for modeling of the antitumor activity. However, topological indices in multiparametric regression yielded excellent models. The

results are discussed using a variety of statistical parameters.

Keywords : Antitumor activity, propanamides, topological index, regression analysis.

Introduction

QSAR is a mathematical model obtained using methodology aiming at predicting properties of molecules from their structures¹. Molecular activities obtained experimentally are digital values but structures are in graphical or pictorial form. Thus molecular topology will help the translation of molecular structures into characteristics numerical descriptors. These descriptors are called topological indices. In recent years, the development of structure-activity relationship for drug compounds using computational methods relies on appropriate representations of molecular structure. The credulity and advantages of topological indices (TIs) is that they may be used in quantitative comparison with physical, chemical or biological parameters of molecules in structure activity relationship investigations¹. A plethora of TIs available in the literature and are nicely mentioned and extensively reviewed². In the present investigation, initially we have used a large of such indices obtained from Dragon software and then we have arrived at a smaller set of useful

descriptors for modeling the antitumor activity of the set of compounds used. The variable solution of regression analysis has been carried out using SPSS (ver-13) software.

Histones are a major protein constituent of chromosomes and play an important role in regulating chromatin structure and thus gene expression. The histone deacetylases (HDACs) are essential for the balance between the acetylated and deacetylated states of chromatin and eventually regulate gene expression. Perturbation of this balance has linked to cancer. Inhibitors of HDACs under exploration are considered because of their potential roles in reversing the silenced genes in transformed tumor cells by modulating transcriptional processes and modeling of some new chemical entities for this series would be better from those available today.

The antitumor activity for the 40 derivatives of N-hydroxy-3-phenyl-2-propanamides was reported earlier³. However, no QSAR study is made up till now. The objective of the present study is, therefore, to attempt QSAR

[†]In honour of Professor Padmakar V. Khadikar.

study on these novel inhibitors of human histone deacetylase with *in vivo* antitumor activity.

Methods and materials

The first step of our study is to transfer the molecular structure into their molecular graph by deleting all the hydrogen from the molecular structure and then to estimate a large series of descriptors using dragon software. Subsequent, we have made variable selection for the correlation of activity with the selected descriptors. Finally we have to obtain statistically significant models⁴. We have to test the precision, reliability and validity of the proposed models. In addition to the goodness of fit and the stability of the model, it is important to evaluate the robustness and the predictive capacity as well as validity of the model before using the model on the interpretation and prediction of the biological activity.

Results and discussion

The molecular structures of 40 compounds used are presented in Table 1 and their activities are given in Table 2. The useful descriptors from the large pool have been taken which are indicated as Polarity Number (Pol)⁷, Reciprocal Hyper-Detour Index (RHYWT)⁸, 3-Path Kier Alpha-Modified Shape Index (S3K)⁹, First Zagreb Index By Valence Vertex Degrees (ZM1V)¹⁰, All-Path Wiener Index (WAP)¹², Eccentric Connectivity Index (CSI)¹¹, Average Connectivity Index Chi-0 (0-Order) ($0\chi_A$)¹³, Valence Connectivity Index Chi-3 (3-Order) ($3\chi_V$)¹³, Mean Information Index on Atomic Composition (AAC)¹⁴, Mean Information Content on The Distance Equality (IDE)¹⁴, Structural Information Content (Neighborhood Symmetry of 0-Order) (SIC '0')¹⁵, Complementary Information Content (Neighborhood Symmetry of 0-Order) (CIC '0')¹⁵. The correlation of activities with the descriptors is shown in Table 3. Using stepwise regression analysis seven statistically significant models were obtained as shown in Table 4. The statistical parameters and quality of correlations of these models are given in Table 5.

Preliminary regression analysis with chemical properties such as molecular weight, molar refraction, molar volume, Parachore, index of refraction, surface tension, density and polarizability calculated from ACD Labs. Software (ver-8) has indicated that none of chemical descriptors and their combination yields any statistically significant model for modeling the activity. Thus, the chemical descriptors are not useful in our drug designing; consequent to this we attempted modeling of the activity using topological indices. The correlation matrix (Table 3)

indicated that none of these descriptors when used single gave statistically significant models. However, in the multi-parametric regression five statistically significant models are obtained for modeling the activities (Tables 4, 5).

A perusal of Table 5 shows that out of the five models attempted, the model-4 (eq. (4)) is the most appropriate model for modeling the activity. The statistical data presented in Table 5 indicate that this model is not only statistically but also has excellent predictive power. The quality factor also favors our findings⁵. This Q is defined⁶ as, the ratio of correlation coefficient R to the standard error of estimation SE i.e. $Q = R/SE$. Thus, higher the value of R, the lower the SE, and the larger will be Q values and better will be quality of the model. The Probable (PE) Error of Coefficient of correlation smaller than R also indicates that propose model is definitely good.

The aforementioned results and discussion indicate that the log IC₅₀, the antitumor activity against enzyme potency of the set of 40 compounds used, is a multidimensional property and cannot be expressed by one dimensional property. Thus, application of Ties and their combinations with other molecular descriptors widens the solution of the problem of providing structural evidences for activity. It is worth mentioning that good statistics alone do not mean that the corresponding models have better predictive potential also. In view of this, we have to use a cross-validation method and calculate various parameters for confirmatory the predictive potential of all proposed model from model number 1 to 5 containing different no. of Ties.

Some other important statistical parameters are also proves the authenticity of the model-4 such as PRESS (Predicted Residual Sum of Squares), SSY (Sum of Squares of Response Value), R^2_{CV} (Cross Validation Correlation Coefficient). The value of ratio PRESS/SSY should be in range of 0.1 to 0.4 for the best predictivity. And corresponding R^2_{CV} value should compile the range of 0.9 to 0.6. In our cases R^2_{CV} has value from 0.6 to 0.8 and the ratio PRESS/SSY from 0.1 to 0.4 for different models, out of them model-4 has this ratio as 0.2 and it has highest predictive capacity.

PRESS is a good estimation of the real prediction error of the model. If PRESS is smaller than the sum of the squares of the response value, the model predict better than others which is statistically significant. A perusal of the data in Table 4 shows that the proposed models are

Table 1. The molecular structure details of secondary amine, set of 40 propanamides compounds

Table-1 (contd)

Compd.	R ₁	R ₂	n	Chemical Structure	H	I
1		H	1		H	1
2		H	1		H	1
3		H	1		H	1
4		H	1		H	1
5		H	1		H	1
6		H	1		H	1
7		H	1		H	0
8		H	1		H	1
9		H	1		H	1
10		H	1		H	1
					H	1
					H	1
					H	1
					H	1

Table-1 (contd.)

25		1	
26		Cyclohexyl	1
27	Do		1
28		-C ₂ H ₄ OH	1
29	Do		1
30		-C ₂ H ₄ OH	1
31	Ph(CH ₂) ₃		1
32		PhCH ₂	1
33		1	
34	Ph(CH ₂) ₃		1
35			
36			
37			

Table-1 (contd.)

38	
39	
40	

Table 2. Activity and log activity of compounds

Compd.	[IC ₅₀] Activity	log IC ₅₀	Compd.	[IC ₅₀] Activity	log IC ₅₀
1	30	1.4771	21	69	1.8388
2	66	1.8195	22	111	2.0453
3	23	1.3617	23	59	1.7709
4	16	1.2041	24	38	1.5798
5	84	1.9243	25	23	1.3617
6	14	1.1461	26	20	1.3010
7	63	1.7993	27	10	1.0000
8	24	1.3802	28	32	1.5052
9	37	1.5682	29	370	2.5682
10	67	1.8261	30	24	1.3802
11	30	1.4771	31	164	2.2148
12	46	1.6628	32	85	1.9294
13	14	1.1461	33	52	1.7160
14	40	1.6021	34	278	2.4440
15	150	2.1761	35	23	1.3617
16	27	1.4314	36	53	1.7243
17	262	2.4183	37	118	2.0719
18	51	1.7076	38	194	2.2878
19	53	1.7243	39	1	0.0000
20	79	1.8976	40	26	1.4150

excellent and out of them model-4 is the most appropriate which have lowest PRESS values.

Further support in favor of this model can be obtained from the value of S_{PRESS} (uncertainty of prediction) and

Table 3. Correlation matrix with respect to log IC₅₀

	log IC ₅₀	P3	ZM1	RHYWT	WAP	IDE	AAC	SIC'0'	CIC'0'	3χV	S3K	0χA	CSI
log IC ₅₀	1												
P3	-0.06840	1											
ZM1	0.14192	0.6579	1										
RHYWT	-0.29075	0.3704	0.0034	1									
WAP	0.12425	0.7345	0.5555	-0.1415	1								
IDE	-0.10289	0.3768	0.4871	-0.0276	0.3886	1							
AAC	-0.00538	-0.2348	-0.1884	0.1944	-0.3491	-0.1148	1						
SIC'0'	0.07782	-0.0061	-0.0638	-0.1031	0.1639	0.0583	0.0597	1					
CIC'0'	0.08140	0.8712	0.6919	0.3405	0.6179	0.3721	-0.4985	-0.1478	1				
3χV	-0.02450	0.9299	0.6893	0.2381	0.7233	0.3236	-0.3877	-0.1194	0.9159	1			
S3K	0.32793	0.0706	0.0841	0.5212	-0.1815	0.0865	0.2172	-0.1477	0.2605	0.0523	1		
0χA	-0.05636	-0.5512	-0.6049	0.1777	-0.6198	-0.5178	0.2844	-0.0027	-0.4838	-0.6200	0.2588	1	
CSI	-0.10100	0.8704	0.7183	0.3035	0.7811	0.6111	-0.2655	-0.0166	0.8200	0.8226	0.1363	-0.6688	1

Table 4. The proposed best models with respect to log IC₅₀

Regression eq. (1), Model-1

$$\log IC_{50} = 10.7903 (\pm 6.6083) - 1.9214E - 03 (\pm 0.0009)*CSI - 4.8531E - 02 (\pm 0.0079)*RHYWT - 2.0897 (\pm 0.5684)*IDE + 1.3768 (\pm 1.6304)*AAC + 3.4001 (\pm 1.0041)*CIC'0' - 0.6054 (\pm 0.1992)*3\chi V + 0.2454 (\pm 0.0636)*S3K - 20.9983 (\pm 6.2062)*0\chi A + 5.1084E - 03 (\pm 0.0012)*ZM1V$$

Regression eq. (2), Model-2

$$\log IC_{50} = 15.8675 (\pm 5.1376) - 2.4029E - 03 (\pm 0.0009)*CSI - 5.0394E - 02 (\pm 0.0079)*RHYWT - 2.0536 (\pm 0.5547)*DE + 2.8028 (\pm 0.7282)*CIC'0' - 0.7438 (\pm 0.2240)*3\chi V + 0.3014 (\pm 0.0583)S3K + 0.2798E - 02 (\pm 0.0283)*P3 - 22.9804 (\pm 6.2316)*0\chi A + 4.7840E - 03 (\pm 0.0012)*ZM1V$$

Regression eq. (3), Model-3

$$\log IC_{50} = 15.6994 (\pm 4.6013) - 4.4494E - 03 (\pm 0.0012)*CSI - 0.0245 (\pm 0.0103)*RHYWT + 3.8143E - 05 (\pm 0.0000)*WAP - 1.3386 (\pm 0.5624)*IDE + 3.1802 (\pm 0.6725)*CIC'0' - 0.6524 (\pm 0.1657)*3\chi V + 0.2970 (\pm 0.0505)*S3K - 26.5841 (\pm 5.8409)*0\chi A + 4.2885E - 03 (\pm 0.0011)*ZM1V$$

Regression eq. (4), Model-4

$$\log IC_{50} = 8.4323 (\pm 5.6063) - 5.1376E - 03 (\pm 0.0012)*CSI - 2.2247E - 02 (\pm 0.0098)*RHYWT + 4.6178E - 05 (\pm 0.0000)*WAP - 1.1926 (\pm 0.5387)*IDE + 2.9851 (\pm 1.4432)*AAC + 4.48291 (\pm 0.8969)*CIC'0' - 0.82703 (\pm 0.1785)*3\chi V + 0.2476 (\pm 0.0536)*S3K - 28.5622 (\pm 5.6276)*0\chi A + 3.1733E - 03 (\pm 0.0012)*ZM1V$$

Regression eq. (5), Model-5

$$\log IC_{50} = 10.1957 (\pm 6.4157) - 2.1171E - 03 (\pm 0.0009)*CSI - 4.7808E - 02 (\pm 0.0077)*RHYWT - 2.0906 (\pm 0.5510)*IDE + 1.4604 (\pm 1.5813)*AAC + 1.9689 (\pm 1.1518)*SIC'0' + 3.5131 (\pm 0.9756)*CIC'0' - 0.5936 (\pm 0.1932)*3\chi V + 0.2538 (\pm 0.0618)*S3K - 21.6363 (\pm 6.0280)*0\chi A + 4.9597E - 03 (\pm 0.0012)*ZM1V$$

Table 5. Statistical parameters

Model-(eq.) no.	R ²	R	PE	K	E	LOF	Q	R ² _{Ad}	RMS
1	0.7504	0.8663	0.0263	0.4996	50.0400	3.9595	3.7978	0.6755	0.1434
2	0.7626	0.8733	0.0250	0.4872	51.2763	3.7610	3.9283	0.6913	0.1283
3	0.8034	0.8963	0.0207	0.4434	55.6604	3.1187	4.4276	0.7444	0.1088
4	0.8286	0.9103	0.0181	0.4140	58.5995	2.8503	4.8715	0.7696	0.2830
5	0.7732	0.8793	0.0239	0.4762	52.3765	3.8901	4.0451	0.6950	0.1424

Table-5 (contd.)

Model-(eq.) no.	LSE		R ² _{CV}	S (press)	SD	AAE	PSE	T(test)	F(test)
	PRESS	SSY							
1	2.1811	8.3308	0.7502	0.2634	0.1484	0.0993	0.2634	10.6930	10.0210
2	1.9768	8.3308	1.7627	0.2567	0.1481	0.0656	0.2223	11.0484	10.7077
3	1.6393	8.3308	0.8331	0.2338	0.1256	0.0572	0.2024	12.0016	13.6190
4	1.3966	8.3308	0.8324	0.2195	0.3324	0.0801	0.1869	13.5537	14.0240
5	1.8901	8.3308	0.7731	0.2553	0.1672	0.0674	0.2174	11.3819	9.8870

R² = Coefficient of variation, R²_{adj} = Adjusted R-Squared, PE = Probable Error of estimation, K = Degree of Lack of Relationship, E = Index of Forecasting Efficiency, LOF = Friedman's Lack of Fit Measured, Q = Quality of Proposed Model, LSE = Least square error. PRESS = Predictive Residual Error Sum of Squares, SSY = Sum of Square of Response Values, R²_{CV} = Cross-validated correlation coefficient. S (press) = Uncertainty of Prediction, SD = Goodness of Fit, AAE = Average Absolute Errors, PSE = Predictive Square Error, T(test) = Significance Level, F(test) = Fischer Statistic, RMS = Root Mean Square of the Errors.

PSE (predictive square error). All these values are given in Table 5. The lowest value of S_{PRESS} and PSE for the model-4 indicates that it has the highest predictive potential.

In the model-4 proposed (Table 7), some of the Ties have positive coefficients and some have negative coefficients. This means that in some cases log IC₅₀ increases

Table-6 (contd.)

Table 6. Hypothetical model for judging the predictive power of the proposed model for set-1 (N-hydroxy-3-phenyl-2-propenamides) derivatives with respect to enzyme potency (IC₅₀)

Compd.	R ₁	R ₂	n
1		1	
2		1	
3		1	
4		-C ₃ H ₇	1

5		1	
6		1	
7		1	
8		1	

Table 7. Calculated activity [IC₅₀] by using the best model-4 used for prediction

Compd.	log IC ₅₀	IC ₅₀
	Cal. Act.	Cal. Act.
1	1.6654	46.2798
2	0.9947	9.8780
3	1.3359	21.6731
4	1.8685	73.8730
5	1.2985	19.8823
6	1.7630	57.9492
7	1.8031	63.5485
8	1.5385	34.5581

Table 8. Statistical parameters for justification of prediction

Model-(eq.)	R ²	R	PE	K	E	LOF	Q	R ² _{ad}	RMS
4	0.84012	0.91658	0.01538	0.399840	60.0150	2.44080	5.27301	0.79691	0.04803
							SEE		
	LSE						SDEC		
Model-(eq.)	PRESS	SSY	R ² _{CV}	S (press)	SD	AAE	PSE	T(test)	F(test)
4	1.45028	9.07157	0.84012	0.039164	0.054568	0.000771	0.173823	15.54721	19.44

with the magnitude of Tles with positive coefficient and vice versa. In model-4 CSI, RHYWT, IDE, 3 χ V, 0 χ A have negative coefficients while WAP, AAC, CIC'0', S3K, ZM1V have positive coefficients. Hence, it can be concluded that the anti-tumor activity of a set of 40 compounds decreases with increasing magnitude of CSI, RHYWT, IDE, 3 χ V, 0 χ A and increases with increasing in the magnitude of WAP, AAC, CIC'0', S3K, ZM1V.

Finally, in order to confirm our findings we have estimated log IC₅₀ using all models from eq. (1) to eq. (5) and compared them with all the actual observed values of log IC₅₀. The correlation of observed and estimated log IC₅₀ i.e. anti-tumor activity are demonstrated in graph plotted along with their tabular form from eq. (1) to eq. (5) giving predictive correlation coefficient in the range of R² 0.8 for model-4.

In order to confirm modeling potential of the proposed model we have designed a new set of 8 compounds not contained in the list of the chosen compounds. These compounds are shown in Table 6. We have used CSI, RHYWT, IDE, AAC, CIC'0', S3K, 3 χ V, 0 χ A, ZM1V, WAP as the correlating parameters for the designing of 8 new compound and calculated log IC₅₀ and subsequently IC₅₀ for these unknown compounds.

Now to examine the predicted activity of these 8 unknown compounds, there are two ways to make sure a judgment. Firstly synthesis the proposed 8 unknown compounds and determine their log IC₅₀ experimentally or secondly to add these compounds to the earlier set of 40 compounds that we have studied the second procedure, thus making a total of 48 compounds. Then we have used the same model-4 in Table 4 and made a new regression analysis. The statistics and predictive power both are improved for the new set of 48 compounds, at this stage we can safely say that our proposed activity for the unknown new 8 compounds are more or less parallel to the

experimental activity.

The details of the regression analysis for the new set of 48 compounds are given in Table 8. On comparison of Table 5 with Table 8, we have observed that when the 8 new compounds are added to the studied 40 compounds, there are drastic improvements in the statistics for the new set of 48 compounds. The comparison has proved the situation much clear.

Thus, we observed that by adding 8 unknown compounds in the regression procedure R² increases from 0.8283 to 0.84012 and subsequently SD reduces from 0.3324 to 0.05456. Hence, an excellent statistics has resulted with the addition of the 8 unknown compounds. We have also observed that R²_{ad} is also increased from 0.7696 to 0.79691 indicating there by that the addition of 8 compounds is well justified. Finally, Q value is also increased from 4.87 to 5.2730 showing that there is improvement in the predictive power by addition of 8 compounds. Now our requirement for synthesizing is under work progress to confirm our theoretically presented log IC₅₀.

Conclusions

Predictive QSAR models which are based on molecular descriptors have been proposed in this study to correlate the activity of compounds. Application of the developed model to a testing set of 40 compounds demonstrates that the new model is reliable with good predictive accuracy and simple formulation.

Since the QSAR was developed on the basis of theoretical molecular descriptors calculated exclusively from molecular structure, the proposed model could potentially provide useful information about the activity of drug compounds.

We have developed here a useful QSAR equation derived from theoretical descriptors (Topological Index). A

MLR is successfully presented for prediction the antitumor activity ($\log IC_{50}$) of various drug compounds with diverse chemical structures using a linear quantitative structure-activity relationship. A model with high statistical quality and low prediction errors was obtained. The macroscopic (bulk) activities/properties of chemical compounds clearly depend on their microscopic (structural) characteristics. Development of quantitative structure property/activity relationships (QSPR/QSAR) on theoretical descriptors is a powerful tool not only for prediction of the chemical, physical and biological properties/activities of compounds, but also for deeper understanding of the detailed mechanisms of interactions in complex systems that predetermine these properties/activities. MLR analysis provided useful equation that can be used to predict the $\log IC_{50}$ of chemicals based upon Topological Index parameters. The results indicate that a strong correlation exists between the $\log IC_{50}$ and Topological Index for drug compounds. This procedure allowed us to achieve a precise and relatively fast method for activity determination of different series of drug compounds and to predict with sufficient accuracy of new drug derivatives. All these results, therefore, suggests that the estimated activity of the 8 unknown compounds is well justified.

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References

1. Anshu Goel and A. K. Madan, *J. Chem. Inf. Comput. Sci.*, 1995, **35**, 504.
2. B. Spilker, "Multinational Drug Companies", 'Issues in Drug Discovery and Development', Raven Press, New York, 1989
3. Stacy W. Remiszewski, Lidia C. Sambucetti, *et al.*, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2003, **46**, 4609.
4. S. Chatterjee, A. S. Hadi and B. Price, "Regression Analysis by Examples", 3rd ed., Wiley, New York, 2000.
5. V. K. Agrawal and Padmakar V. Khadikar, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2002, **12**, 3981.
6. M. Thakur, A. Thakur and Padmakar V. Khadikar, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2005, **15**, 203.
7. J. R. Platt, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1947, **15**, 419
8. M. V. Diudea, *J. Chem. Inf. Comput. Sci.*, 1997, **37**, 292
9. L. B. Kier, *Quant. Struct. Act. Relat.*, 1985, **4**, 109
10. I. Gutman, B. Ruscic, N. S. Trinajstic and C. F. Wilcox (Jr.), *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1975, **62**, 3399.
11. V. Sharma, R. Goswami and A. K. Madan, *J. Chem. Inf. Comput. Sci.*, 1997, **37**, 273.
12. I. Lukovits, *J. Chem. Inf. Comput. Sci.*, 1998, **38**, 125.
13. L. B. Kier and L. H. Hall, "Molecular Connectivity in Structure-Activity Analysis", Research Studies Press, Letchworth, 1986.
14. D. Bonchev, "Information Theoretic Indices for Characterization of Chemical Structures", Rsp-Wiley, Chichester, UK, 1983.
15. "Studies in Physical and Theoretical Chemistry". C King, R.B., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1983, 178-191